

A Review Study on Methane Gas Sensors

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

With the rapid development of coal industry, the hidden danger of coal safety production in China is becoming increasingly prominent, mainly in the coal mine gas exceeding the standard seriously. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor the gas in real time to control the gas concentration. At present, most mines in our country use catalytic gas sensor, which is easily affected by the bad field environment of coal mine, with poor acquisition accuracy and serious zero drift. It needs to be corrected every certain time, which not only increases the maintenance cost, but also reduces the data acquisition accuracy. At the same time, the catalytic sensor is prone to catalyst poisoning, so the service life of the sensor is short. The infrared gas sensor uses infrared spectrum to detect the target gas, which is basically not affected by the industrial environment. The double channel sampling technology can restrain the zero drift. Compared with catalytic gas sensor, infrared gas sensor has higher accuracy and reliability, especially suitable for harsh industrial environment such as coal mine. This paper is review on the current innovation and process of work of Methane sensors

Keywords: METHANE SENSORS, DEVELOPMENT, COAL MINE

Introduction

In recent years, the main component is methane, accident become the first hand of coal mine safety. The key to control the serious accident of coal mine it is to prevent and contain gas accidents by nail effect roof, and solve gas outburst and explosion. In addition to the rule of gas formation, explosion characteristics, outburst mechanism, gas explosion and gas explosion. It is necessary to strengthen the monitoring of the side of the reservoir; this is the top priority of coal mine safety production. In this section, the UF reliability and sensitivity of methane sensor are connected to coal. The reliability and sensitivity of the mine safety monitoring system can satisfy the safety monitoring system of the coal mine the eyes of the system, methane monitoring, felt the role of the soul Pest prediction Lack of technical equipment.

Infrared gas detection technology is mainly based on different gas in different concentrations of infrared spectrum absorption is not the same? The sensor head is composed of a light source, a sampling gas chamber, a thermoelectric detector head of a movable channel and a thermoelectric detector head of a

reference channel. The signal generated by the thermoelectric detector depends on the change of the incident radiation after the gas absorbs the infrared spectrum.

2. Present and past study

At present, most of the methane sensors used in domestic coal mines use carrier relay (catalytic combustion type). Although this method can be used for TOS detection, it has the fatal weakness of short life, poor working stability and frequent adjustment of JFI. For coal mines with carrier catalytic type, it is necessary to first establish a safety measurement and control instrument box repair room, and then calibrate the carrier catalytic sensor with calibration gas and air samples every 15 days. After the methane concentration sensor is impacted by more than 4, it must be adjusted or replaced in time.

At the same time, the environment of high dust and high humidity in coal mine environment accelerates the aging of R carrier catalytic sensor, which seriously restricts the technical and accurate detection of gas. Because the weakness of carrier catalytic methane detection method cannot be solved in Shanxi, Europe and the United States and other developed countries have been studying the application of infrared absorption light potential technology for many years, and finally launched the infrared methane sensor for coal mine in 2004. As soon as the product is launched, it has been attached great importance by all countries. Compared with the carrier catalysis method, the infrared absorption method has better stability, reliability and longer pregnancy life: It is an ideal product of methane sensor for coal mine, and has a good development prospect; however, the promotion of this product in China has encountered a lot of problems. First of all, these products in China's mine I pa high dust, high humidity environment cannot be used normally; Secondly, these products are very expensive; At the same time, these products are not compatible with the existing safety inspection system of domestic Mou mine.

3. Way the Methane Sensors works

The infrared methane sensor is based on the fact that methane has a very strong absorption peak to the infrared light with the wavelength of 230 μm , while the water vapor and carbon dioxide in the impurity gas that affect the herdsman have no obvious absorption spectrum. Measuring the optical absorption of gas fraction is an effective method for gas species identification and gas fraction concentration determination. The spectral gas sensing technology used in coal mine infrared methane sensor is precisely based on the spectral consistency between the vibration /rotation absorption characteristic spectrum of methane molecule or pan chin /multi-platform absorption spectrum line and the emission spectrum of light source. When the infrared light passes through the gas to be side, the infrared light at the wavelength of 230 μm FFL of methane has a very strong absorption. Figure 1.1 shows Methane-gas-detection-system-block-diagram.

Figure 1.1: Methane-gas-detection-system-block-diagrams

As shown in Figure 1.2, the light emitted by the visible light infrared light probe is reflected in the air chamber and then divided into two filters to enter the infrared sensor, of which, one is the reference path, and the other is the reference path. There is no absorption in the other lobe, which is the measurement pathway. It has a strong absorption peak, which is the ratio of the output signal of the channel. It is related to the concentration. By comparing the output signals of the two channels, the concentration of methane can be obtained.

Figure 1.2: Gas sensing procedure

4. Innovation of methane sensors

The innovation of infrared methane sensor in technology is shown in several aspects of F. The differential compensation signal processing is used to test the methane concentration of 0-100% full range.

Polypropylene micro porous air filter membrane is used as dust-proof and moisture-proof protective membrane of infrared methane sensor in coal mine, which can solve the problem of dust-proof and water-proof of r-sample gas sensor. Polypropylene micro porous film is a special new material. There are only 9 billion microspores on the surface of the film, and the diameter of microspores is 0.2-3 PM. Even the smallest powder cannot pass through the film. This kind of material is made by special technology_ Excellent chemical stability, smooth surface, easy to clean dust, no aging, good air permeability, oil and water repellent. Figure 1.3 shows the modules used in gas sensors

Figure 1.3: Modules used in gas sensors

It is suitable for high concentration, high temperature and dust environment. Because the multi-layer micro porous membrane can be used for surface filtration, the dust will not penetrate into the fabric; therefore, the phenomenon of R-block was eliminated. The starting current of the infrared methane sensor is controlled within 150mA. Because of the complexity of the circuit and the large number of components, the main reason is the high power consumption of the light-emitting devices. The light source will present a low resistance coil when the power is K. The starting current of the system is large. Figure 1.4 shows the innovative method of Gas sensing.

Figure 1.4: Inventions in Gas sensing

The starting current of foreign similar products is generally not less than 250mA, which puts forward more requirements for the power supply capacity of the equipment. We choose constant current power supply mode to solve the problem of large starting current. At the beginning of power on, the power supply outputs a low voltage to the light-emitting element, so that the initial current of the light-emitting element remains constant. Then, the power supply voltage is increased in sequence until the normal power supply. After the light pool works stably, the rain supplies power to the display and transmission output circuit. It has been proved that this method can be used to suppress the starting current. JFI was used to improve the speed of gas fast conversion. In the process of white light modulation, the light source generates heat. The micro oscillation of gas flow in the gas chamber is formed when the acceleration e is switched periodically, which improves the gas dust interaction ability of the gas chamber. The detection accuracy of methane is improved by using R small constant white light source, single beam, double wavelength and optical narrow-band transition technology. We use the method of single beam and double beam, which can compensate the baseline drift of the measurement signal, caused by environmental gas interference, light intensity change and other factors, and improve the anti-interference ability of the sensor. The gas chamber temperature compensation method of the sensor is adopted. The range of FL is increased by increasing the temperature of T-cell. Temperature has a great impact on infrared gas analysis, and it is a complex nonlinear pod system, which must be caused by the temperature change of infrared gas sensor network.

The influence of temperature on infrared gas analysis, it is difficult to establish the mechanism transverse type, so it is necessary to obtain the scattered data through the test beam for modeling. Firstly, the relationship between the methane clarity value at a specific temperature and the output concentration of infrared methane sensor is established, and then the relationship between the temperature and the voltage of infrared methane sensor is established. After a long time test, the mathematical model of temperature connection is determined, which can ensure the accuracy of the sensor. Figure 1.5 shows the principal method of gas sensing.

Figure 1.5: Principal method of gas sensing

The infrared methane sensor adopts double CPU control mode. The system runs stably and reliably. In order to improve the accuracy of the consistency, it is necessary to compensate the non-linear modulation signal and the temperature environment of the sensor. We use a special DSP for front-end signal processing. At the same time, we use a thoroughfare CPU to complete alarm, setting, remote control, output and other functions. This not only solves the problem of large operation panel, but also shortens the transmission distance of front-end analog signal, and avoids the interference caused by R analog signal transmission process.

5. Conclusion

The infrared methane sensor is suitable for the coal mines with complex gas content in Shangshan sulfur mine and other coal mines. The traditional catalytic combustion coal mine gas detection equipment can hardly be used in the high sulfur coal mine due to its limitation. Therefore, some high sulfur coal mines do not install the coal mine gas monitoring system, which causes great hidden danger to the safety production. Infrared methane sensor is not affected by any gas. It can not only be used in coal mines with high sulfur content, but also work stably and reliably in other more complex gas environment, which fundamentally solves the problem of gas detection in complex gas environment.

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